

CoBiol-A pathway to decarbonization and public engagement at large

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MSCA and CoBiol

The transport sector arises as one of the largest consumers of fossil fuels, accounting for 40% of the final energy consumption of which 80% relates to road transport. Subsequently, this results in an annual release of 7 billion tons of greenhouse gases (GHG), mainly carbon dioxide (CO₂) and nitrogen oxide (NO_x), contributing to potentially catastrophic changes in climate, environment, biodiversity, and public health. To achieve a cleaner and healthier environment, there is a strong focus on the development of sustainable low-carbon, high yield, and cost-competitive liquid bio-crude oil as an alternative to conventional fossil crude oil [1]. Particularly as outlined in the Renewable Energy Directive (RED), EU set an ambitious target to increase the share of renewable energy in the transport sector up to 10% by 2020 and decrease GHG to 40% compared to 1990 levels by 2030.

Under this frame, the CO-HTL4BIO-OIL project (branded CoBiol), an EU-H2020 funded ambitious project under Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA-IF), is working to meet these challenges with a dense research plan. CoBiol complete title is: “Catalytic co-

hydrothermal liquefaction of binary and ternary mixtures of rye straw, shellfish, and beef tallow for sustainable production of high-grade biocrude-oil to drop-in transport fuel”. The project was conceived and lead by Fatma Marrakchi, and it was hosted by Aalborg University, Denmark, Advanced BioFuel research Group at AAU Energy department from December 2020 to February 2023.

CoBiol@Research

As shown in Figure 1, the CoBiol project addresses a number of key-issues, providing pioneering insights into looking for more valuable management methods of carbonaceous food waste streams that have the added potential of producing salable, surrogate and competitive fuel for petroleum oil and reducing the environmental cost associated with their disposal. Scaling of the catalytic co-hydrothermal liquefaction (CO-HTL) process for continuous operations and employing novel predictive quantitative models based on biomass composition and HTL process variables aim at enhancing the yield/quality of biocrude-oil, provide an estimate of techno-economic analysis, and serve as a great perspective for biorefinery integration.

Fig.1: Outlook of CoBiol project

Shellfish, such as crab waste, one of the by-products that CoBiol project experimented on, consists of 20%–50% calcium carbonate (CaCO_3), 20%–40% protein, and up to 15%–40% chitin. Based on “The EU Fish Market” published by the European Market Observatory for Fisheries and Aquaculture Products (EUMOFA), the EU total production exceeds 6 to 8 million tons of shellfish, and approximately 750,000 tons of crab shells are wasted every year. Shellfish are often just dumped in landfills or returned to the sea [2]. However, this approach is not economically viable for many businesses as traditional disposal routes become increasingly restricted and expensive at £60–£300 per ton. To target the circular economy, CoBiol explored the thermocatalytic route for turning crab waste into biofuels via a two-step process: first through hydrothermal liquefaction (HTL) to obtain a biocrude oil, followed by catalytic upgrading [3] to obtain drop-in fuels. Smashed crab waste (20 kg) was provided by Polar Seafood Company. The fed slurry was pumped to a continuous unit at a flow rate of 0.5 L/h. It was directed first to a preheater at 200 °C, then to a pressurized reactor at 250 bar. The main reactions of crab waste conversion took place for 15 min at 350 °C. The HTL products were collected at a sampling temperature of 60 °C. The HTL process was successfully operated for more than 30 hours. The obtained HTL products were 35% of biocrude

oil, 40% of aqueous phase, 20% of solid residues, and 5% of gases. When characterizing the produced biocrude oil by using an elemental analyzer apparatus (CHNO analysis), the bio-oil contained 79% of C, 12% of H, 5% of O, and 4% of N. Therefore, further catalytic upgrading should be considered to remove the residual O and N compounds and make the biofuel meet transportation specifications.

CoBiol@School

CoBiol did not feature only research activities but also included a significant focus on communicating research to a general audience. This effort was embodied by CoBiol@School: an outreach activity to bring CoBiol@Research close to the public, impact, and share the wonder of science with young generations. CoBiol@School is a five-activity learning session:

Activity One is a dialogue, The Soul of CoBiol, where pupils were engaged to get answers to the question “What is CoBiol?”.

Activity Two is a story titled Find Your Radiance! It consists of 3 parts, starting from Marie Curie’s Story to Making Marie Curie, and finally Her Story (“Her” refers to Fatma). Activity Three is a CoCreate game, presenting the cocreation of three consecutive games called Search (Crossword), Puzzle, and Discover (Cards).

Fig. 2: Continuous HTL of crab waste

Activity Four is a poem “The NextGen Heroes!” with an enthusiastic message, aiming to raise awareness in the young audience by transmitting long-term objectives of building a sustainable planet.

Activity Five is a Tour in the Advanced Biofuel Lab where the pupils visited lab-scale and continuous HTL, hydrotreater, and distillation units.

The first CoBiol@School activity was held at AAU Energy on April 27th, 2023, and saw the participation of 24 enthusiastic pupils (Key Stage 7) from the Skipper Clement Skolen at Aalborg.

Figure 3. A banner for the 1st CoBiol@School activity was held at AAU Energy on April 27th, 2023.

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References

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- [3] D. Castello, M. Haider, L. Rosendahl, Catalytic upgrading of hydrothermal liquefaction biocrudes: Different challenges for different feedstocks, Renewable Energy. 141 (2019) 420–430.

Learn more about CoBiol Project:

CORDIS
EU research results

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/895710>

<https://www.cobiol.energy/>

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/cobiol/>

<https://www.youtube.com/@cobiol3576>

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